

Demo: Towards Reliable Cloud-native 5G and Beyond Networks using In-Network Computing

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Abstract—Emerging use cases, such as Tactile Internet, typically demand high reliability and low-latency communication. To fulfill these stringent requirements, 5G networks employ retransmission within the Radio Access Network (RAN) in the event of packet loss, but at the expense of increased latency. An alternative approach to address this challenge involves leveraging Random Linear Network Coding (RLNC) to recover lost packets, thereby eliminating the necessity for retransmission within the RAN. We demonstrate the ability of in-network computing to run RLNC, particularly with the use of RLNC recoder, to enhance reliability and reduce latency within the network.

Index Terms—Tactile Internet, Random Linear Network coding, 5G, Cloud-Native, Reliability, Low-Latency.

I. INTRODUCTION

Future mobile networks have been expected to support various use cases, such as Tactile Internet. Meanwhile, Telco operators have embraced cloud computing technologies and Network Function Virtualization (NFV) [1] for both the core and the Radio Access Network (RAN) to build cloud-native 5G and beyond networks, enabling innovation and faster time-to-market by decoupling software functionalities from physical hardware and running the network functions on generic hardware. However, it is challenging for the cloud-native 5G and beyond networks to meet the strict requirements of emerging use cases that demand Ultra-Reliable Low-Latency Communication (URLLC) [2].

In mobile networks, wireless communication within the RAN is the most challenging aspect in terms of reliability and latency. To address this challenge, the RAN employs the Acknowledged Mode (AM) for retransmission, addressing packet loss and ensuring overall reliability. This involves the gNodeB (gNB) retransmitting the lost packets back to the UE. However, the use of AM introduces significant latency due to the retransmission process [3].

Recent studies [3] have been proposed to eliminate the need for retransmission within the RAN. Instead, they employ Random Linear Network Coding (RLNC), a Forward Error Correction (FEC) mechanism, to ensure reliability without introducing adverse delays. The authors seamlessly integrated RLNC into the cloud-native 5G as an additional feature, avoiding any disruption to the existing infrastructure and associated protocols of 5G components. The outcomes demonstrate a notable enhancement in both reliability and delay. This study

Fig. 1. A simplified 5G network architecture with the support of RLNC.

considers an *encoder* to generate coded redundant packets and a *decoder* to recover any lost original packets using the coded redundant packets. However, packet loss typically occurs in the network due to various reasons such as network congestion or lossy channels. This problem becomes exacerbated when transferring packets over large networks. Therefore, the use of encoder and decoder is insufficient to ensure high reliability, especially in the cloud-native 5G and beyond networks. Other studies [4]–[6] implemented the full-stack RLNC (*encoder*, *recoder*, and *decoder*). Notably, the recoder is used at intermediate network nodes to participate in the coding process, thus improving the network reliability. However, none of the previous studies considers the recoder in the cloud-native 5G and beyond networks.

In this work, we show the benefits of using In-Network Computing (INC) for the deployment of RLNC, particularly the recoder, to improve the reliability of cloud-native 5G and beyond networks. Specifically, we demonstrate the ability of INC computing to run the recoder in an intermediary node (on a Cisco Catalyst 9500 switch) between encoder and decoder. The recoder randomly linearly combines incoming packets with existing packets in its buffer and sends them to the decoder to recover any lost packets.

II. TECHNOLOGY

We aim to demonstrate the potential of using in-network computing to deploy RLNC recoder to improve the reliability of the cloud-native 5G and beyond network. Toward this aim, we first present the integration of RLNC into the cloud-native 5G and beyond network. We then describe the use of in-network computing to deploy the recoder.

Fig. 1 shows the integration of RLNC, specifically highlighting the RLNC recoder, into the cloud-native 5G and beyond network consisting of Core Network (CN), gNodeB (gNB), and User Equipment (UE). We consider that UEs are significantly far from the gNB, necessitating the use of one or

Fig. 2. Testbed architecture for the integration of RLNC into the OAI, particularly with the use of the *recoder*.

more relays to expand coverage [7]. Encoder first generates coded redundant packets by combining original packets in a generation with random coding vectors and sending them along with the original packets to the UPF in the CN. The UPF forwards the original and the coded redundant packets to the gNB by using GPRS Tunneling Protocol (GTP). Then, gNB sends the original and the coded redundant packet over the air to the relay node. This relay node consists of an in-network computing switch on top of which recoder is run. Each packet that recoder receives i) will be stored in the recoder’s buffer for that generation, ii) randomly linearly combined with existing packets in the buffer, and iii) sends the combined coded packet to the UE. The decoder at the UE uses the combined coded packets it received from recoder to recover any lost or corrupted packet. Therefore, the use of the recoder increases the probability of successful transmission of packets to the decoder.

To have a transparent deployment of the RLNC recoder within the network, we incorporate in-network computing technology. This technology allows network devices to perform complex tasks in addition to their basic switching and routing functions. This means that programs that usually run on end hosts can run on network devices (e.g., switches and routers). We select the Cisco Catalyst 9500 switch, which has the capability to host and run recoder as a Docker container inside the switch. By deploying the recoder on the switch, it autonomously processes the traffic passing through. This approach ensures the recoder can automatically add encoded packets to recover any missing packets before the traffic goes to the next hop or reaches its destination. Also, this setup eliminates the necessity to modify network routing configurations or direct the flow to an external recoder on a separate server.

Fig. 3. Demonstration GUI.

III. DEMONSTRATION

For the implementation of our demo, we used OpenAirInterface (OAI)¹, which is 3GPP compliant, to build a cloud-native 5G and beyond network. We deploy all 5G components as Docker containers to facilitate our implementation. Fig. 2 shows the integration of RLNC into the OAI, particularly with the use of the recoder. Our demo setup includes four physical computers with Docker (version 24.0.1) installed to run the containers, and a Cisco Catalyst 9500 high-performance switch to connect the four computers and also serve as an in-network computing device to run the recoder Docker container. To connect all Docker containers, we created three Docker networks as follows: *i*) two overlay networks used separately for control traffic and data traffic between the 5G components, and *ii*) one MacVLAN network² used to connect the OAI components with the recoder running on the switch. To simulate realistic packet loss we used iptables to introduce a random packet loss of 15% at the Relay, and 20% random loss between the recoder and the decoder. To automate the deployment, we used Docker Compose (version 2.17.0) to deploy the OAI and RLNC components on the four computers. To deploy the recoder on the switch, we used Cisco app-hosting commands that run Docker under the hood³. We used Audio, Video, and Haptic traffic captured as PCAP files from a real environment to simulate real situations and results. We used tcpreplay (version 4.4.2) [8] to replay the captured traffic in PCAP files. The traffic generated by tcpreplay at EXT-DN is sent to the encoder, which adds new coded packets to the original traffic. The encoded traffic then goes through the CN (i.e. UPF and gNB) until it reaches the Relay. The Relay forwards the traffic to the recoder using the MacVLAN network. The recoder, which runs on the switch, combines the traffic with old packets in the buffer and sends it to the decoder at the UE. The decoder uses the coded packet to recover any missing packets.

¹<https://gitlab.eurecom.fr/oai>

²<https://docs.docker.com/network/drivers/macvlan/>

³<https://blogs.cisco.com/networking/application-hosting-on-catalyst-9000-series-switches>

Fig. 4. Video traffic's (a) OWD and (b) packet loss measurements.

Fig. 5. Audio traffic's (a) OWD and (b) packet loss measurements.

Using our GUI shown in Fig. 3, users can actively engage with the demonstration through the web GUI to customize and try different tests. Users can initiate interaction with the demonstration by selecting different traffic types, such as Audio, Video, and Haptic. Furthermore, they can choose from three distinct 5G setup scenarios: i) Scenario 1, representing the pure OAI deployment without any RLNC components; ii) Scenario 2, incorporating OAI with integrated RLNC encoder and decoder functions; and iii) Scenario 3, featuring OAI along with RLNC functions including encoder, recoder, and decoder, with the recoder operating on the switch. Upon initiating the demo by clicking the start button, the backend dynamically adjusts the configuration of components according to the chosen traffic type and scenario. This involves configuring the routing of traffic to adhere to the designated path, and subsequently, tcpreplay commences the replay of the corresponding PCAP file associated with the user's selected traffic type. While the demo is running, the GUI will display various network performance indicators such as the number of transmitted packets, number of received packets, packet loss, and One-Way Delay (OWD); which is the time needed for a packet to be transmitted from the EXT-DN (source) to the UE (destination). After running the three scenarios, the user can notice that scenario 3, which involves the use of the recoder, has the lowest packet loss among the three scenarios while introducing similar OWD compared to Scenario 2.

In addition to the results for haptic traffic observed in Fig. 3, we plot the OWD and packet loss for video traffic as another example, shown in Fig. 4, to further demonstrate the potential of the recoder. The results show that without network coding

the packet loss for video traffic is 32.7%. Using encoder and decoder alone can reduce the packet loss to 13.8%. However, the integration of recoder further reduces the packet loss to 0.5%. Similarly, without network coding audio traffic has a packet loss of 32% and with only encoder and decoder the packet loss is 13.4%. Whereas including recoder decreases the packet loss for audio traffic to 1%. As observed in Fig. 4 (b) and Fig. 5 (b), the inclusion of recoder achieves sharp decrease in packet loss without costing much additional latency when compared to no recoder network coding case regardless of whether the traffic is audio or video.

IV. CONCLUSION

We demonstrate the potential of using in-network computing technology to deploy RLNC *recoder* within the network to improve the reliability of cloud-native 5G and beyond networks. We used a Cisco Catalyst 9500 High-performance switch as an in-network device to host and run the *recoder* in a transparent manner, where the *recoder* recodes incoming traffic to increase the probability of recovering any missing packets at the destination. The demonstration can be potentially extended to support other emerging use cases in cloud-native 5G and beyond networks.

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